

Blockchain and the music industry" and "Hacker meets Security".

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Developing an Internet concept is not everything. Neither is profit. My drive comes from bringing the two together. Taking action in real-time so that we generate enough money today to remain competitive tomorrow. Being effective not only for yourself but for the people that depend on you to be extremely focused and creative. With over 10 years of experience in ICT Concept Development and Online Marketing I have developed several high-profile websites, mobile apps and social media campaigns for companies all over the world. The combination of expertizes from the fields of Entertainment, ICT and Telecommunication bring a unique out of the box perspective on everyday challenges and needs. Making my input valuable to every project.

Author biography

Phill Tevreden Awar-winning internet entrepreneur of suriname and co-founder Fissacoin and founder Wlove B.v. Constantly learning with an open mind focus to deliver results.

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